

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of rice planting date and density on weed growth

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Weed growth was observed in an experiment during kharif (wet season) 1975, 1976, and 1977 at the Crop Research Centre (29° N, 79.3° E, 243.84 m altitude). Treatment 1 had shortduration varieties Ratna, Rasi, and Cauvery planted 10 June. Treatment 2 had Ratna planted 20 June, Rasi planted 5 July, and Cauvery planted 10 July so all varieties would mature at the same time. Medium-duration variety Jaya was planted 10 June to mature with treatment 2. Treatments were tested at plant density of 25, 100, and 400 hills/m².

Increasing plant density from 25 to 100 hills/m² decreased weed dry weight and intensity significantly (see table). Planting dates did not influence weed weight. The interaction of planting date and plant density significantly affected weed growth. □

Weed growth (av of 3 seasons) in rice planted at different dates and plant densities, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Treatment	Weed growth	
	Dry weight (g/m ²)	Intensity (no. of weeds/m ²)
Planting scheme		
Jaya, 10 June	15.6	8.9
Ratna, 10 June	15.5	9.1
Rasi, 10 June	14.9	10.7
Cauvery, 10 June	15.3	10.1
Ratna, 20 June	14.7	9.7
Rasi, 5 July	14.8	10.1
Cauvery, 10 July	14.4	9.7
S.Em ±	0.8	0.2
C.D. (P = 0.05)	ns	0.7
Plant density (hills/m ²)		
400	2.6	1.9
100	10.1	10.7
25	32.4	16.6
S.Em ±	0.6	0.3
C.D. (P = 0.05)	1.8	0.9

Effect of nitrogen fertilizer and weed management on performance of four rice varieties in Sudan Gezira

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Low soil nitrogen content and severe upland weed infestation are major constraints to high dry-seeded rice yields in Sudan Gezira. A field study at Gezira Research Station in 1980 evaluated grain yield of 4 rice varieties (see table) with different plant height and maturity, and grown at 2 levels of nitrogen (70 and 140 kg N/ha) under poor, medium, and good weed management levels. Twenty-four treatments were arranged in a ran-

domized complete block design with four replications.

Medium-maturing varieties IR2035-242-1 and IR2053-206-1-3 outyielded early-maturing IR2061-552 and IR1561-228-3-3. Under good weed management, however, grain yields were similar. Grain yield of early-maturing rices was substantially reduced by poor weed management.

Nitrogen level significantly affected grain yield. Application of 140 kg N/ha increased grain yields 19-30% over those obtained with 70 kg N/ha, depending on the variety. Grain yield was consistently and progressively increased with better weed management. Unrestricted weed growth significantly decreased number

Effect of nitrogen levels and weed management on grain yields and yield components of four rice varieties at Sudan Gezira, 1980.

N (kg/ha)	Weed management	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1,000-grain wt (g)
<i>IR1561-228-3-3 (early maturity, short stature)</i>						
70	Poor	66	0.6	282	53	20.4
70	Medium	63	2.7	342	62	20.1
70	Good	70	3.4	369	60	19.7
140	Poor	66	0.9	267	61	20.0
140	Medium	70	2.6	329	58	19.9
140	Good	72	4.9	396	76	19.8
<i>IR2061-552 (early maturity, medium stature)</i>						
70	Poor	72	0.7	254	43	20.9
70	Medium	75	2.2	342	58	21.2
70	Good	82	3.2	367	62	21.5
140	Poor	78	0.5	255	52	22.7
140	Medium	78	2.1	329	65	21.2
140	Good	88	4.0	374	61	21.9
<i>IR2035-242-1 (medium maturity, short stature)</i>						
70	Poor	65	1.5	284	56	22.1
70	Medium	68	2.7	342	67	21.8
70	Good	69	3.9	355	65	22.7
140	Poor	77	2.1	304	66	22.4
140	Medium	74	4.1	382	69	23.1
140	Good	79	4.9	392	73	22.5
<i>IR2053-206-1-3 (medium maturity, medium stature)</i>						
70	Poor	84	1.6	294	75	23.3
70	Medium	86	2.8	332	80	23.3
70	Good	84	3.5	319	83	23.2
140	Poor	85	1.7	291	73	23.6
140	Medium	95	4.0	366	83	23.9
140	Good	99	4.8	472	92	23.5